

ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL FACTORS AFFECTING THE TRANSPORT GEOGRAPHY OF TASHKENT REGION

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Abstract. *This article discusses the economic and social factors affecting the foundation and development of transport geography, taking an example of Tashkent region. It has shed light on the general landscape of the region's transport geography, and has provided some supporting examples having a considerable effect on the above-mentioned issue.*

Keywords: *economic and social factors, development, changing into the regional area, workforce, population density, industrial regions, objects of social sphere.*

In economic and social geography, several factors affect the formation, generation, and development of territorial production networks in a certain area. There are several factors that influence the foundation of transport geography. In many literatures related to the field, the location and density of the population, the terrain of the area, the state of development of the area, the location of industrial enterprises, the availability of raw materials and labor force, and the transit possibilities of the area are mentioned as the factors that cause the placement of transport systems.

In recent years, the following factors are suggested which influence the location of transport roads and transport network in scientific works:

- natural conditions (terrain, climate, hydrographic objects, the layer of soil);
- level of socio-economic development of a particular area;
- location and culture of the population living in the area and changing the place into the inhabited one;
- political-geographic features;
- main traffic flows and their directions;
- configuration of the transport network;
- characteristics of the area served by the transport network (the shape and size of the area, diversity of the level of the area, type of neighborhood).

It is obvious that in science (especially in geography) it is expected that dividing into regions, analysing the object which is being observed in more parts, is absolutely important to explain any object in a deeper and more precise way for effective study. Based on this theory, it is required to study the geography of transport in more detail not only within the geographical area, but also in terms of the administrative-territorial border. It is important to imagine the landscape of the transport geography of Tashkent region, analyze the placement of transport systems, classify and analyze the factors affecting its establishment.

Tashkent region is the place bordering from the north and north-west to the Republic of Kazakhstan, from the north-east Kyrgyz Republic, from the east Namangan province. from the

south it borders with Republic of Tajikistan, although it borders with the Syrdarya region from the west and has led to the development of road transport in the mountainous regions, there are also a number of railways that pass through the territory of the region, which can be useful, too. The length of railways in Tashkent region is 354.2 km. The railway line connecting the independent countries of Central Asia with the cities of Eastern Europe (including Moscow-Tashkent-Turkmanboshi) passes through the territory of the region. The railway lines in the direction of Angren city and Chorvok town start from Tashkent. Railways around Tashkent are electrified. Since 2004, the Tashkent-Samarkand electric passenger train has been running. The region has a dense network of highways. The total length of highways of the region is 6.6000 thousand kilometres (in particular, covered with hard surface is 5.9 thousand km). The total length of highways of regional importance is 6,600 km (including 5,900 km of paved roads). Important highways: Great Uzbekistan tract, Tashkent-Andijan-Osh-Kashkar highway.

The length of public highways in Tashkent region is 3955.0 km, of which 400 km are the highways for international purposes, 1241.0 km are the national highways, and 2314.0 km are roads for local purposes. An analysis of international highways passing through the province reveals that they are mainly roads that pass through the capital city of Tashkent and connect them with the cities of the neighboring republics. M-34 "Tashkent - Dushanbe", M-39 "Alma ata - Bishkek - Tashkent - Shahrisabz - Termiz", M-39 b Tashkent ring road can be mentioned.

At the same time, these roads pass through the province: 163.0 km of the road A-373 "M39 highway, through Gulistan-Bo'ka-Angren-Ko'kon and Andijan to O'sh, and a road, A-373 a "M39 road's 45 km additional road passing through Guliston-Bo'ka-Angren-Andijan into O'sh-Tashkent.

The territorial factor, the construction of highways in the province, plays an important role in the location of highways in the region by the direct connection with the capital city of Tashkent, connecting the eastern regions of the republic (Fergana, Namangan and Andijan) with the central regions (Jizzakh, Syrdaryo). Industrial regions and points also have a significant impact on the formation of regional transport systems.

In particular, Tashkent-Chirchik, Tashkent-Yangiyol, Angren-Almalik industrial regions and Bekobod industrial hubs, created in the region, have influenced the formation of the transport geography. The main part of the Tashkent-Chirchik, Tashkent-Yangiyol industrial regions is the city of Tashkent, which includes Chirchik, Yangiyol industrial hubs, as well as small and medium-sized cities such as Ghazalkent, Piskent, Nurafshan, Chinoz, Keles. A large part of socio-economic development and economic connections of these cities are directly related to the capital, which is reflected in the transport systems and their movement. If we analyze the location of population, the average population density in the region is 157 people per 1 km². The population of the region is densely populated from Chorvok to Syrdarya, especially in the Tashkent agglomeration, which consists of a chain of several large cities. Most of the cities in the Tashkent region surround the capital forming a ring, which has been a strong impetus to the formation of transport systems in the investigating area. Also, the location of industrial enterprises in regional cities should be mentioned as one of the main factors. There are 7 cities in the region, and Nurafshan, the regional center, has a total of 880 LLCs, of which there are 4 large enterprises. There are a total of 1487 LLCs in Almaliq, an industrial city. There are 10 large operating enterprises. 2130 LLCs are registered in the city of Angren, located in the eastern part of the region. The number of large enterprises is 11. 1072 LLCs are registered in the city of Bekobod, which is located in the south-west of the region. The number of large enterprises is 5 in the area. Relatively smaller and less

populated city of Ohangaran has 847 LLCs and 3 large enterprises. 2095 LLCs are registered in Chirchik, another large industrial city. There are 14 large enterprises. If the purposes of activity of the enterprises in Yangiyol are analysed, it can be seen that this city mainly specializes in the food sector. In recent years, the establishment of educational institutions in the region is one of the factors that have diversified the transport geography of the region.

It can be clearly seen this situation in the example of Chirchik in the region. The establishment of Chirchik State University in the city, the transplantation of the Uzbekistan State University of Physical Education and Sports to this city, and the opening of the private Tashkent University of Economics and Pedagogy can be described as the factors for the further activation and intensification of transport activities. It is also clear that the private higher educational institutions established in the cities of Almalyk and Angren of the region will have their influence in the future.

Тошкент вилоятида аҳолининг сони, турли таълим ва соғлиқни сақлаш муассасалари (мактабгача таълим, умумий ўрта таълим, академик лицей ва касб-ҳунар мактаблари, оилавий поликлиникалар, хусусий шифохоналар ва ҳк) ҳам муҳим омиллардан саналади. (1-жадвал)

In Tashkent region, the number of population, various educational and health institutions (preschool education, general secondary education, academic lyceum and schools, family polyclinics, private hospitals, etc.) are also important factors. (Table 1)

Social indicators of districts and cities of Tashkent region

	city/district name	population number	Number of NCA	educational institution				Number of MF	station number
				Number of PEI	Number of SEI	Number of AL and VC	university number		
1	Nurafshan	51,4	22	12	13	1	-	2	46
2	Almalyk	133,4	51	41	24	4	2	6	42
3	Angren	191,3	51	50	46	6	-	10	38
4	Bekabad	96,9	35	32	20	2	-	6	11
5	Ohangaran	39,9	21	16	9	1	-	1-	21
6	Chirchik	162,8	44	33	25	3	2	9	16
7	Yangiyol	61.7	18	23	13	2	-	1	9
8	Oqqorghan	107689	29	16	50	2	-	1	154
9	Ohangaran	97968	29	18	51	3	-	1	77
10	Bekabad	161446	51	35	59	2	-	1	120

11	Bostonlik	172210	59	26	54	4	-	6	184
12	Bo'ka	129256	42	21	54	4	-	3	143
13	Quyichirchik	111240	37	31	52	3	-	1	209
14	Zangiota	160458	85	47	43	3	1	11	183
15	Yuqorichirchik	136046	47	38	41	3	-	2	135
16	Kibray	171797	88	59	48	3	3	14	116
17	Parkent	159545	58	31	53	3	-	2	130
18	Piskent	103217	27	26	42	2	-	1	81
19	O'rta Chirchik	132285	62	23	62	4	-	4	144
20	Chinoz	138418	55	28	49	3	-	5	77
21	Yangiyol	211793	69	37	55	4	-	4	196
22	Toshkent	186443	68	45	31	4	-	5	107

The location of international customs posts connecting with neighboring countries (Kazakhstan, Tajikistan) also affects the geography of transport in the region. It is possible to go to the Republic of Tajikistan through the customs posts located in the city and district of Bekobod, and to the Republic of Kazakhstan through the customs posts located in the Tashkent district. This situation ensures the activity of vehicle traffic in these directions. (Table 2)

Table 2

Border crossing points in Tashkent region

Tashkent region customs department	post «Yallama»	round the clock	Kazakhstan
	post «Navoiy»	round the clock	Kazakhstan
	post «S.Nayimov»	round the clock	Kazakhstan
	post «Oybek»	round the clock	Tajikiston
	post «Bekobod avto»	daytime	Tajikiston
	post «G'ishtko'prik»	round the clock	Kazakhstan
	post «Farhod»	daytime	Tajikiston
	post «Bekobod»	round the clock	Tajikiston
post «O'zbekiston»	round the clock	Kazakhstan	

In terms of railway transport, it should be noted that along with Bekobod - Tashkent (via Syrdarya region), Tashkent - Ghazalkent and Tashkent - Angren routes, and all routes connecting the capital with the central cities of the Republic and neighboring countries pass through the territory of the region should also be mentioned.

The important sectors of the region - energy, mechanical engineering, metallurgy, coal, mining metallurgy, chemical industry, footwear, cotton ginning, food industry, textile and processing of agricultural products have also affected the location of regional transport.

Also, as the factors influencing the formation of transport systems in the region, climatic features of the region, topography (rising from the southeast to the northeast), rivers passing through the territory of the region (Syrdarya, Piskent, Chirchik, Ohangaron), irrigation canals (Bozsuv, Tashkent, Dalvarzin, Karasuv) and water reservoirs ("Tuyabogiz", "Ohangaran" and "Chervok") can be classified which have also had a significant influence.

The location of children's camps such as "Chimyon", "Burchmulla", "Boughiston", "Khumson", "Aqtosh", climatic resorts and rest houses in the territory of the region is the reason for the construction of transport routes and the movement of tourist flows in these directions.

The activity of "Angren Logistics Center" JSC, established in 2014 in Tashkent region, also serves to increase its transport potential. "Angren Logistics Center" JSC carries out cargo operations by solving issues related to cargo storage, loading and unloading, fast and high-quality transportation, customs documents. JSC "Angren Logistics Center" also provides expedition services in the direction of Southeast Asia through the ports of Iran, Russia, and China.

The construction of the railway network on the Uzbekistan-Kyrgyzstan-China route, which is a promising project, will serve to further improve the transport infrastructure of the region.

The city of Tashkent, which is directly adjacent to the Tashkent region, is the main transport hub of the country. There are routes from Tashkent to suburban areas, other cities of our country and cities of foreign countries by road, rail and air transport.

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